

Effects of Brain-Based Strategy On Ekiti State Senior Secondary School Students' Learning Outcomes in Biology

Author(s), FALEMU, Funke Aina

Abstract:

The study examined the effects of brain-based strategy and conventional method on learning outcome of senior secondary school students in Biology in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study specifically examined the difference between the academic performance of students exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method before and after treatments; and the difference between attitudinal mean scores of students exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method before and after treatment. This study adopted a pre-test, post-test, control group quasi experimental design in which two groups (one experimental group and one control group) was involved. The sample consisted of class intact size (139 students offering Biology) drawn from 6 public secondary schools in Ekiti State. The sample was selected using multistage sampling procedure. Two instruments tagged Performance Test in Biology (PTB) and Biology Attitudinal Scale (BAS) were used for collecting the data for the study. The face and content validity of the instrument was ensured by experts of Tests and Measurement and Biology Education. The study was carried out in three phases namely pre-treatment stage, treatment Stage, and post-treatment stage. Hypotheses 1 - 4 were tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that students exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method were homogeneous at the commencement of the study but there

EASIJ

Accepted 4 August 2022

Published 27 August 2022

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7029398

was improvement in performance and attitude of students exposed to brain-based strategy after intervention. It was recommended that brain-based strategy should be incorporated as a strategy of teaching Biology in secondary schools.

Keywords: Brain-based Strategy, Performance, Attitude, Biology,

About Author

Author(s):

FALEMU, Funke Aina

Department of Science Education,
School of Science Education,
College of Education,

Bamidele Olumilua University of Education, Science and Technology,
Ikere Ekiti, Nigeria.

funkefalemu01@gmail.com

Introduction

Biology, in particular is central to many of the scientific fields of human endeavours and its teaching should be given a serious attention. The study of Biology helps in the appreciation and enjoyment of nature and life. In addition, it prepares students for professional careers in such fields, as, medicine, bio-technology, agriculture and pharmacy. Biology is the science which studies living things and concerns itself with the study of the structure, behaviour, distribution, the origin of plants and animals and their relationship with their environments.

Biology is offered at the Senior Secondary School (senior secondary school One (S.S.S 1) to senior secondary school three (S.S.S 3) classes) as a single subject. This group of students must have offered Basic Science and Technology at the Junior Secondary School (J.S.S 1 – 3) which is aimed at preparing them for core science subjects at the Senior Secondary level.

Evidences have shown that students are not doing well in Biology at both West African Secondary School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) and National Examination Councils Secondary School Certificate Examination (NECO/SSCE). In Ekiti State, the average performance of students at credit level and above in Biology from 2015 to 2019 was less than 49%. Reports have shown that the Senior Secondary School Biology results in WASSCE and NECO SSCE in the last five years (2015-2019) in Nigeria were generally not encouraging. In 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018 and 2019 only 41.10%, 43.02%, 42.61%, 46.19% and 45.02% respectively, obtained credit pass and above in Biology. The same trend of low performance was reported in NECO/SSCE Biology results for Nigeria from 2015 to 2019. In 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018 and 2019 only 49.81%, 50.04%, 49.44%, 49.11% and 50.81%, obtained credit and above in Biology. Similarly, the Senior Secondary School Biology results of Ekiti State between 2015 and 2019 were also generally not encouraging as the percentage of candidates that passed Biology at credit level and above in Ekiti State were below 49%.

Aside the performance of students, attitude could also be a measure of learning outcome of students. Attitude can be formed as a result of some opinion or by following examples of someone like parents, teachers, peer group and friends. Michael and Gwyneth (2015) defines attitude as the way a person behaves towards something that show how the person feel or think about something. Attitude is a learned pre-disposition or tendency on the part of an individual to respond positively or negatively to some object, situation, concept or another person. Attitude can be acquired through learning and can be changed through persuasion using variety of techniques (Sarmah & Puri, 2014). Attitude to Biology plays a crucial role in the teaching and learning of Biology. It affects students' performance in Biology. Usually, the way Biology is represented in the classroom and perceived by students, even when teachers believe they are presenting it in authentic and context dependent way stands to alienate many students from Biology. It appears that positive attitude to Biology could lead students to success in Biology.

This level of performance of students in Biology may likely be associated with the use of conventional method of teaching and students' attitude to Biology. Despite several researches

advocating for the use of innovative methods, students' performance in Biology is still not encouraging. Therefore, researchers in Biology education have continually sought for better teaching methods that will enhance students' performance.

The quest to curtail the shortcomings of the conventional method used in teaching and learning of Biology led to the discovery of other innovative teaching methods, among which is the brain-based strategy. Brain-Based Learning instructional strategy is a learner-centered and teacher-facilitated strategy that utilizes learners' cognitive endowments. This instructional strategy is based on the structure and functions of the brain in different aspects such as learning, assimilating, thinking and remembering. Brain-Based Learning is defined as any teaching strategy that utilizes information about the human brain to organize how lessons are constructed and facilitated with emphasis placed on how the brain learns naturally. It is a method for developing creative solutions to problems. It is an open sharing activity which encourages all students to participate. Brain-Based Learning involves accepting the rules of how the brain processes, and then organizing instruction bearing these rules in mind to achieve meaningful learning (Duman, 2010; Duman, 2014).

The Brain-Based Approach displays how teachers can create environments for active learning, taking into account how the brain learns, which is critical for students' learning (Caine, et al., 2009). Learning, in brain, is a process which starts with the reception of incoming information by the sensory memory. The information is first sent to the thalamus. Then, it is either sent to the cortex for analysis and response, or sent to amygdala (short-term memory) for scanning and storing in the memory. Then the information is sent to hippocampus (long-term memory). In order for information to be conveyed from the short-term memory to the long-term memory, strategies such as repetition should be used (Huen & Chan, 2010). Since learning occurs in the brain in this way, learning environments should be designed in line with the brain-based learning principles. The brain-based learning involves acknowledging the brain's rules for meaningful learning and organizing teaching with those rules in mind.

Caine and Caine cited in Huen and Chan (2010) explained that, brain-based learning involves accepting the rules of how the brain processes and then organizing these rules/principles in mind to achieve meaningful learning. Caine and Caine (2002) define brain-based learning as recognition of the brain's codes for a meaningful learning and adjusting the teaching process in relation to those codes. The principles of brain-based learning propose that effective learning could occur only through practicing real life experiences. Learning becomes more expressive when the brain supports the processes in search of meaning and patterning. Accordingly, it enables the learners to internalize and individualize learning experiences. Therefore, it is essential that learners be encouraged to participate in the learning and teaching process actively and that teaching materials be chosen according to their learning preferences.

Thus, there is the need to look at the effects of using brain-based strategy to teach Biology, probably it could be promising to better performance in biology. Evidences abound that

brain-based strategy could be used to effectively facilitate better performance in Biology. It appears that the conventional method does not give attention to individual differences. This study, therefore, is a response to this challenge, and it is aimed at investigating the effects of brain-based strategy on students' learning outcome in Biology.

The study examined the effects of brain-based strategy and conventional method on learning outcome of senior secondary school students in Biology in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study specifically examined:

- i. the difference between the academic performance of students exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method before and after treatments; and
- ii. the difference between attitudinal mean scores of students exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method before and after treatment.

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were generated for this study.

1. There is no significant difference between the pre-test mean score of students in Biology exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method.
2. There is no significant difference between the post-test mean score of students in Biology exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method.
3. There is no significant difference in the attitudinal mean score of students exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method before treatment.
4. There is no significant difference in the attitudinal mean score of students exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method after treatment.

Research Method

This study adopted a pre-test, post-test, control group quasi experimental design in which two groups (one experimental group and one control group) was involved. The homogeneity of the groups was established by pre-test while post-test was used after the treatment to measure learning outcomes (academic performance and attitude). The population of the study comprised of all S.S.S. 2 students offering Biology in all the public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The sample consisted of class intact size (139 students offering Biology) drawn from 6 public secondary schools in Ekiti State. The sample was selected using multistage sampling procedure.

Two instruments tagged Performance Test in Biology (PTB) and Biology Attitudinal Scale (BAS) were used for collecting the data for the study. PTB was used to measure students' performance in Biology. It consists of Sections A and B. Section A sought for the bio-data of the respondents which include the name of the school, identification number, school location and gender. Section B of PTB consisted of 30 objectives items with four options. The PTB was used for both pre-test and post-test for data collection. Biology Attitudinal Scale (BAS) investigated the affective domain of the students in Biology. The instrument consists of Sections A and B. Section A sought student's personal information while Section B consisted

of 25 items covering the disposition of the students to Biology. The items are rated on a 4-point Likert Scale: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The face and content validity of the instrument was ensured by experts of Tests and Measurement and Biology Education. To carry out the research in the schools, the researcher obtained permission from the authorities of the six schools. The study was carried out in three phases namely pre-treatment stage, treatment Stage, and post-treatment stage. The data collected through the instruments were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Hypotheses 1 - 4 were tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the pre-test mean score of students in Biology exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method.

Table 1: t-test Analysis for difference in the performance of students in Biology exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method before treatment

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	P
Brain-based	71	10.21	2.18	137	1.350	0.319
Conventional	68	9.73	2.01			

P>0.05

Table 1 shows that the t-cal value of 1.350 was not significant because the P value of 0.319 was greater than 0.05 level of significance. This implies that null hypothesis is not rejected. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the pre-test mean score of students in Biology exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method. The implication of this finding is that the students exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method were homogeneous at the commencement of the study.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the post-test mean score of students in Biology exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method.

Table 2: t-test Analysis for difference in the performance of students in Biology exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method after treatment

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	P
Brain-based	71	24.84	4.09	137	12.797*	0.000
Conventional	68	16.72	3.37			

*P<0.05

Table 2 shows that the t-cal value of 12.797 was significant because the P value of 0.000 was less than 0.05 level of significance. This implies that null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference between the post-test mean score of students in Biology exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method. Students exposed to brain-based strategy performed better than the students exposed to conventional method with a mean difference of 8.12.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the attitudinal mean score of students exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method before treatment.

Table 3: t-test Analysis for difference in the attitude of students towards Biology exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method before treatment

Variations	N	Mean	SD	Df	t _{cal}	P
Brain-based	71	51.76	2.54	137	1.827	0.081
Conventional	68	50.99	2.43			

P>0.05

Table 3 shows that the t-cal value of 1.827 was not significant because the P value of 0.081 was greater than 0.05 level of significance. This implies that null hypothesis is not rejected. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the attitudinal mean score of students exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method before treatment.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in the attitudinal mean score of students exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method after treatment.

Table 4: t-test Analysis for difference in the attitude of students towards Biology exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method after treatment

Variations	N	Mean	SD	Df	t _{cal}	P
Brain-based	71	83.51	2.65	137	64.822*	0.000
Conventional	68	55.68	2.41			

*P<0.05

Table 4 shows that the t-cal value of 64.822 was significant because the P value of 0.000 was less than 0.05 level of significance. This implies that null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference in the attitudinal mean score of students exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method after treatment.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that students exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method were homogeneous at the commencement of the study but there was improvement in performance of students exposed to brain-based strategy after intervention. There was significant difference between the post-test mean score of students in Biology exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method. This finding is in line with the findings of Duman (2010), Akyurek and Afacan (2013), and Yagcioglu (2014) as they concluded that brain-based teaching strategy significantly impact students' performance in science.

It was also revealed that there was no significant difference in the attitudinal mean score of students exposed to brain-based strategy and conventional method before treatment while there was improvement after intervention for students exposed to brain-based strategy. This finding is in consonance with the findings of Saleh (2011), Yagcioglu (2014), and Seyihoglu

and Kaptan (2012) as they concluded that brain-based strategy significantly impact students' attitude toward learning challenging science content.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that, brain-based strategy was more effective and reliable than the conventional method in exhibiting students' performance in and attitude towards Biology. Therefore, brain-based strategy should be incorporated as a strategy of teaching Biology in secondary schools. The employer of Biology teachers should expose them to appropriate workshop on the use of brain-based strategy.

References

- Caine, G., & Caine, R. (2002). *The brain, education, and the competitive edge*. Lanham, MD: Scarecrow Press
- Caine, R., Caine, G., Klimek, K., & McClintic, C. (2009). *Brain/mind learning principles in action: Developing executive functions of the human brain* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press.
- Duman, B. (2010). The effects of brain-based learning on the academic achievement of students with different learning styles. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 2077-2102.
- Duman, B. (2014). Effects of brain-based learning on academic achievement: A sample case of in-class application. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 41, 91-115.3499403
- Huen, M., & Chan, W. (2010). *In motivating and enhancing student learning: A preliminary exploration of an evidence-based practice of brain-based learning (BBL) Intervention Strategies*. Hong Kong: Pui Tak Canossian College
- Saleh, S. (2011). The effectiveness of brain-based teaching approach in dealing with the problems of students' conceptual understanding and learning motivation towards physics. *Educational Studies*, 38(1), 19-29.
- Sarmah, A., & Puri, P. (2014). Attitude towards mathematics of the students studying in Diploma Engineering Institute (Polytechnic) of Sikkim, *Journal of Research and Method in Education*, 4 (6), 6-10.
- Seyihoglu, A., & Kaptan, S. Y. (2012). The effect of brain-based learning approach to elementary teacher candidates' attitude and achievement in geography lesson. *Hacettepe University Journal of Education*, 42, 380-393.
- Yagcioglu, O. (2014). The advantages of brain-based learning in ELT classes. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 152, 258-262. doi:10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.09.190

Cite this article:

Author(s), FALEMU, Funke Aina, (2022). "Effects of Brain-Based Strategy On Ekiti State Senior Secondary School Students' Learning Outcomes in Biology ", **Name of the Journal:** Euro Afro Studies International Journal, (EASIJ.COM), P, 23 –31. DOI: [www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7029398](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7029398) , Special Issue, Issue: 8, Vol.: 4, Article: 3, Month: August, Year: 2022. Retrieved from <https://www.easij.com/all-issues/>

Published By

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International (TWCMSI)

